

Chromones and Flavones. Part VI*. Some Studies on the Iodination of Flavones and Flavanones

U. K. Jagwani and Suresh Sethna

Some hydroxyflavones and their methyl ethers have been iodinated with iodine and iodic acid or with iodine and ammonia and the structures of the products determined by their hydrolysis to the known iodoacetophenone or iodobenzoic acid derivatives.

Some flavanones have also been iodinated and their structures established by converting them to the corresponding flavones or by hydrolysis as in the case of the iodoflavones.

Shah and Sethna¹ studied the iodination of 5-hydroxy- and 7-hydroxy-flavones. The same has now been extended to several other flavones and flavanones.

7,4'-Dihydroxyflavone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid or with one mole of iodine and ammonia provided the 8-iodo derivative, the methyl ether of which on hydrolysis with ethanolic potash afforded the known 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone¹. On iodination with two moles of iodine and ammonia, a di-iodo derivative was obtained. Hydrolysis of its dimethyl ether with ethanolic potash yielded 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4-methoxybenzoic acid¹, indicating that one of the two iodine atoms was in the 8-position. The other fragment containing the side phenyl nucleus could not be isolated from the reaction mixture after hydrolysis. The 8,3'-di-iodo structure has been tentatively assigned to the di-iodo derivative. This is also supported by the result of hydrolysis of the tri-iodo derivative (*vide infra*).

With three moles of iodine and ammonia, 8,3',5'-tri-iodo derivative was obtained which on methylation and subsequent hydrolysis with ethanolic potash furnished the known 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone¹ and 4-methoxy-3,5-di-iodobenzoic acid. The latter was synthesised by iodination of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, followed by methylation and subsequent hydrolysis of the ester formed.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavone was iodinated by Jurd² with iodine and iodic acid to furnish the 8-iodo derivative. On iodination with three times the theoretical amount of iodine and iodic acid, the 6,8-di-iodo derivative was obtained. Its methyl ether on the usual hydrolysis provided the known 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3,5-di-iodobenzoic acid¹. No tri-iodo derivative could be obtained.

7,4'-Dimethoxyflavone on iodination even with excess of iodine and iodic acid yielded only the 8-iodo derivative, as seen by direct comparison with the compound described above.

* Part V, this *Journal*, 1964, **41**, 347.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3899.

2. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1961, 322.

5,7-Dihydroxyflavone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid or with excess of the reagent furnished a di-iodo derivative. Its methyl ether did not provide a coumarone derivative³. Therefore 6,8-di-iodo structure has been assigned to the compound. Chen *et al.*⁴. prepared 5,7-dimethoxy-8-iodoflavone indirectly through the corresponding iodochalkone.

6-Hydroxyflavone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid or with one mole of iodine and ammonia provided a mono-iodo derivative to which the 5-iodo structure has been tentatively assigned in view of the results obtained by earlier workers in the work on coupling of 6-hydroxyflavone with diazotised aniline⁵. Attempts to synthesise 5-iodo-6-hydroxyflavone from 5-amino-6-hydroxyflavone by diazotisation and Sandmayer's reaction failed as on diazotisation the diazonium oxide separated. No di-iodo derivative could be obtained even with a large excess of iodine and iodic acid. 6-Methoxyflavone could not be iodinated at all.

Iodination of flavanones has been studied by a few workers. Seshadri *et al.*⁶. iodinated 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-, 5,7-dimethoxy-, and 5-hydroxy-7,3',4'-trimethoxyflavanones. Wheeler *et al.*⁷ iodinated 5,7,3',4'-tetramethoxy- and 5-hydroxy-7,3',4'-trimethoxyflavanone. Kulkarni *et al.*⁸ iodinated 5',7,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavanone. No other work on iodination of flavanones appears to have been reported.

It appears from the present study that simple flavanone could only be iodinated with a large excess of iodine monochloride, in a poor yield, to 3-iodoflavanone. This has been converted to simple flavone by refluxing with acetic acid and potassium acetate⁶.

7-Hydroxyflavanone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid and with iodine and ammonia provided 3-iodo derivative which was converted into 7-hydroxyflavone by refluxing with potassium acetate and acetic acid. With double the amount of iodine and iodic acid, the 3,6-di-iodo derivative was obtained which on refluxing with potassium acetate and acetic acid furnished 7-hydroxy-6-iodoflavone. Its methyl ether on hydrolysis with ethanolic potash afforded 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-iodoacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-iodobenzoic acid¹.

The same 3,6-di-iodo derivative was obtained by further iodination of 7-hydroxy-3-iodoflavanone with either of the iodinating agents.

4'-Hydroxyflavanone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodinating agents furnished in all cases the 3',5'-di-iodo derivative. Its methyl ether on the usual hydrolysis furnished 3,5-di-iodo-4-methoxybenzoic acid, described earlier.

7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavanone on similar iodination provided 3,6-di-iodo derivative which with potassium acetate and acetic acid furnished the 6-iodo derivative, the methyl ether of which on hydrolysis with ethanolic potash gave rise to 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5-iodoacetophenone¹.

3. Limaye *et al.*, *Rasayanam*, 1956, 2, 97; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 5084.

4. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 85.

5. Iyer and Venkatraman, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, 23A, 278.

6. *Ibid.*, 1949, 30A, 151; 1950, 32A, 17; 1954, 39A, 254; 1955, 41A, 210; 1958, 47A, 184.

7. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 5271.

8. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 24.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Iodination Procedures: (a). *With Iodine and Iodic Acid.*—The flavone or flavanone derivative was dissolved in minimum quantity of warm ethanol and the requisite amount of iodine was added. To the warm dark coloured solutions, thus obtained, the required amount of iodic acid, dissolved in water, was added with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 hr. and the iodo derivative separating either as such or on dilution with water was crystallised from ethanol.

(b). *With Iodine and Ammonia.*—To flavone or flavanone derivative, dissolved in dilute ammonia, a solution of iodine in potassium iodide in requisite quantity was added with stirring at the room temperature during half an hour. The reaction mixture was poured into excess of dilute ice-cold sulphuric acid. The precipitated iodo derivative was crystallised.

(c). *With Iodine Monochloride.*—To the flavone or flavanone derivative, dissolved in minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid, was added requisite quantity of iodine monochloride and the reaction mixture was kept for 24 hr. at 50°. The iodo derivative separating from the solution as such or on dilution with water was crystallised.

TABLE I

Products obtained on iodination.

Iodinating agent.	Product.	M.P.	Formula.	% Yield.	Iodine.		
					Found.	Reqd.	
A. Flavones.							
7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-	a	6, 8-Di-iodo-	283°	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₄ I ₂	47	48.7	48.8
7,4'-Dihydroxy-	a,b	8-Iodo-	233°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₄ I	52	33.2	33.4
"	b	8,3'-Di-iodo-	254°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₄ I ₂	48	50.2	50.2
"	b	8,3',5'-Tri-iodo-	283-85°	C ₁₅ H ₇ O ₄ I ₃	31	60.1	60.3
5,7-Dihydroxy-	a,b,	6,8-Di-iodo-	284°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₄ I ₂	32	50.0	50.2
6-Hydroxy-	a,b	5-Iodo-	208°-200°	C ₁₅ H ₉ O ₃ I	60	35.0	34.9
B. Flavanones.							
Simple	c	3-Iodo-	123°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ I	..	36.7	36.3
7-Hydroxy-	a,b	3-Iodo-	192°	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₃ I	33	35.2	34.7
"	a,b	3,6-Di-iodo-	187°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ I ₂	40	51.6	51.6
4'-Hydroxy-	a,b,c	3',5'-Di-iodo-	178-79°	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ I ₂	33	51.5	51.6
7-Hydroxy-4'-methoxy-	a,b	3,8-Di-iodo-	201°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ I ₂	70	48.4	48.6

*All the melting points are uncorrected. Hydroxy derivatives start decomposing 20-30° below their melting points and melt finally at the mentioned temperature.

Preparation of Methyl Ethers.—The hydroxy-iodo derivatives were methylated by refluxing their acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

Conversion of 3-Iodoflavanones to the Corresponding Flavone Derivatives.—To the 3-iodoflavanone derivative, dissolved in glacial acetic acid, was added potassium acetate and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The product separating as such or on dilution was crystallised.

7-Hydroxy 6-iodo 4'-methoxyflavone.—To 3,6-di-iodo-7-hydroxy-4'-methoxyflavanone (0.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), was added potassium acetate (1 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1½ hr. and then poured on ice-cold water. The product separating was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 280-83°. (Found: C, 48.6; H, 2.6; I, 32.0. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4I$ requires C, 48.7; H, 2.8; I, 32.2%).

TABLE II

Methyl ethers.

Flavone.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Iodine.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
7,4'-Dimethoxy-8-iodo-	264-65°	$C_{17}H_{13}O_4I$	49.0	50.0	3.0	3.2	31.3	31.1
7,4'-Dimethoxy-6,8-di-iodo-	247°	$C_{17}H_{12}O_4I_2$	38.5	38.2	2.3	2.3	47.2	47.5
7,4'-Dimethoxy-8,3'-di-iodo-	272-73°	$C_{17}H_{12}O_4I_2$	38.5	38.2	2.2	2.3	47.8	47.0
7,4'-Dimethoxy-8,3',5'-tri-iodo-	315°	$C_{17}H_{11}O_4I_3$	30.7	30.9	2.0	1.7	58.2	57.7
5,7-Dimethoxy-6,8-di-iodo-	209°	$C_{17}H_{12}O_4I_2$	38.2	38.2	1.9	2.2	48.1	47.6
6-Methoxy-5-iodo-	204-206°	$C_{16}H_{11}O_3I$	50.7	50.8	2.7	2.9	33.5	33.8
4'-Methoxy-3',5'-di-iodoflavanone	147°	$C_{16}H_{12}O_3I_2$	37.9	37.9	2.1	2.4	49.9	50.2

7-Hydroxy 6-iodoflavone.—To 3,6-di-iodo-7-hydroxyflavanone (0.5 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), potassium acetate (1 g.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr. and then poured into ice-cold water. The product separating was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 294°. Jurd³ reported m.p. 304°. (Found: C, 49.2; H, 2.1; I, 34.5. $C_{15}H_9O_3I_2$ requires C, 49.4; H, 2.5; I, 34.9%).

3,5-Di-iodo-4-hydroxybenzoic Acid.—*p*-Hydroxybenzoic acid (0.5 g.) was iodinated with iodine (2.54 g.) in presence of ammonia as usual. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute acetone, m.p. 262°. (Found: I, 65.0. $C_7H_4O_3I_2$ requires I, 65.1%).

Methyl 3,5-Di-iodo-4-methoxybenzoate.—3,5-Di-iodo-4-hydroxybenzoic acid (1 g.) in acetone (100 ml) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (2 g.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) for 8 hr. The product obtained on removal of acetone was washed with a dilute solution of NaOH and the residue was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 93°. (Found: C, 26.0; H, 2.1; I, 60.9. $C_9H_6O_3I_2$ requires C, 25.8; H, 1.9, I, 60.8%).

3,5-Di-iodo-4-methoxybenzoic Acid.—Methyl 3,5-di-iodo-4-methoxybenzoate (0.2 g.) was refluxed with EtOH-NaOH (20%, 25 ml) on a water bath for 2 hr. The product obtained on acidification was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 255°. (Found: C, 23.6; H, 1.9; I, 62.7. $C_9H_6O_3I_2$ requires C, 23.8; H, 1.5; I, 62.9%).